

WRENCH

Whispers of Time

Heritage as Narratives of Climate Change

D1.4 Risk management plan

A Belmont Forum Project

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introduction

WRENCH is a project that addresses the risks associated with climate change. However, risk is a broader concept, and scholars like Ulrich Beck and Anthony Giddens have theorized the notion of the "risk society" as an underlying condition of our times. In light of events such as the pandemic and ongoing wars, it becomes evident that risk is interconnected with various aspects of the current socio-ecological and political crisis.

Foreseeing risk is not an easy task. Scientists define it as the product of three factors: 1) the probability that an event occurs; 2) exposure; and 3) vulnerability. However, we argue that the mainstream approach lacks the inclusion of at least one additional factor: the perception and awareness that people have toward risk, as well as their ability to organize to defend themselves. For instance, communities that are more aware of risk may be better equipped to mobilize resources and advocate for protective measures.

Without entering into this intricate debate, **this deliverable aims to explore how risk, in very general terms, could affect the WRENCH research project.**

Risk management for the WRENCH project represents an ongoing process of self-assessment at the Consortium level.

The Principal Investigator (PI), along with all partners, will engage in risk identification, risk analysis, and risk response. This risk management plan is drafted by the end of the first year to assess project performance along specific dimensions that can affect implementation.

This assessment helps identify critical risks and may require specific measures to address substantial variations, including targeted mitigation actions.

We will consider that new risks can arise at any time during the project's lifetime. In order to keep the risk management plan up to date, our priority is to constantly monitor the successful management and implementation of the project. To this end, we adopt the following key "project performance parameters" to guide us throughout implementation and enable us to identify any critical risks and necessary mitigation actions (based on the H2020 MIGNEX project), as stated on the following page.

Project performance parameters

- **Time:** It is a crucial dimension in project implementation. This critical factor requires monitoring whether the schedule of tasks and deliverables is being followed, if the resources allocated to specific tasks are appropriate, and if deliverables will be submitted on time.
- **Cost:** For each partner, it is essential to ensure that appropriate financial resources are available and allocated for each task and deliverable. In the event of unforeseen discrepancies between allocated resources and actual costs incurred by a partner, appropriate remedies need to be discussed.
- **Impact of the project:** Knowledge transfer and community engagement must be supported and motivated, including after the project ends. We will share project results (databases, reports, training materials) as Open Datasets.
- **Quality:** The Consortium aims to ensure the highest quality of its results, and a strong review process will be implemented by all the partners in turn.
- **Joy:** It is important to maintain enthusiasm, creativity, and dedication during project implementation. The project represents a significant opportunity for all team members to take positive steps in their careers by learning and developing new skills.

Assessment of the parameters in WRENCH

- **Time:** Risk analysis will be carried out on the WP and the Consortium level and prompt reporting of potential problems to the PI will be important to enable swift corrective actions (for example, considering re-allocating resources) to be taken.
- **Cost:** Financial monitoring will be ensured together with continuous assistance to all members of the Consortium, especially for those activities that are based on the involvement of non-academic partners and with the organisation of public events, workshops, etc.
- **Impact of the project:** All stakeholders will apply their expertise to tackle possible issues related to participation and attendance. Their direct involvement as endorsers of the project reduces the likelihood of this risk.
- **Quality:** All WP leaders will be involved in the quality monitoring process. To this end, draft versions of all deliverables will be circulated internally for peer-review.
- **Joy:** Frequent communication with all team members will be ensured. This will create opportunities for open discussions about challenges and time constraints as well as creating a collegial atmosphere that makes it possible to identify problems and to address them as quickly as possible.

risk response plan and monitoring

Event	Probability	Impact on the project	Mitigation action
Delay in access to case studies and pilot sites	Medium	High	<i>Meetings with local stakeholders to readjust the activities</i>
Lack of coordination between project partners	Low	Medium	<i>Regular online meetings and engagement of all the partners in project activities</i>
Delay in in-situ surveys and tests (WP3-4)	Medium	High	<i>Regular meetings with the pilot site coordinator and rearrangements in the work plan</i>
Delay with numerical analyses (WP3-4)	Medium	Medium	<i>Use of alternative softwares</i>

Event	Probability	Impact on the project	Mitigation action
Problems with experimental testing (WP3)	Medium	High	<i>Regular laboratory visits with the involved researchers and technicians; Use of alternative testing techniques; Design new testing layouts; Replace laboratory tests with high-fidelity numerical simulations</i>
Lack of participation and engagement from stakeholders	Medium	High	<i>Mobilise resources to support participation (covering costs, schedules, logistics, etc.); Select venues to increase visibility for individuals and institutions (through a clever communication strategy); Provide incentives to involve diverse sectors (opportunities for publications; grants incubators; educational credits; etc.).</i>
Accessibility to the heritage sites	Medium	High	<i>Some heritage sites can be closed to the public from time to time, making our research difficult. The team will evaluate the possibility of waiting for the reopening of the site and eventually move to another site, given that the main characteristics of the old and new site will be highly compatible</i>
A researcher in the team can move to another institution	Medium	Medium	<i>Nowadays, academic lives are highly mobile. WRENCH has a mixed team with senior and early career scholars, in order to find a balance between more and less mobile researchers. Local teams always include more than one researcher, so to secure the continuation of the project.</i>

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